

PEOPLE-BASED ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT TRANSFORMATION IN EMPOWERING MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN SOUTH SULAWESI. (MAKASSAR CITY CASE STUDY)

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Abstract

Makassar City is an attractive city with potential for developing trade in goods and services. The empowerment of SMEs and the tourism sector in Makassar significantly impacts economic growth, both individually and as a whole. This study aims to determine the role of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in developing a people's economy. In this study, researchers focused on the variables of labor absorption, business capital, and the level of business profits obtained by SMEs, which are independent variables that influence community welfare. The results of this study, using the SPSS approach, provided statistical test results showing that all three variables have a positive and significant influence on community welfare (Y). These include: labor absorption (X1) with a coefficient of $b_1 = 2.019$, followed by business capital (X2) with a coefficient of $b_2 = 2.546$, and finally, business profit (X3) with a coefficient of $b_3 = 3.024$. Meanwhile, in the partial (F) test, the labor absorption variable (X1) was the most dominant, followed by the business capital variable (X2) and business profit variable (X3), each of which influenced the level of community welfare (Y). Both partial and simultaneous tests using SPSS showed an influence of all three variables on community welfare, assuming other variables remained constant.

Keywords: Transformation, Economy, Democracy, Empowerment, Economy.

INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a crucial role in the Indonesian economy, particularly in developing the people's economy. They contribute to all sectors, increasing labor absorption and reducing unemployment. The MSME sector has been promoted and prioritized in regional economic development, proving resilient during the 1998 economic crisis.

Only the MSME sector survived the economic collapse, while larger sectors collapsed. Mudradjad Kuncoro, in the *Bisnis Indonesia* daily on October 21, 2021, stated that MSMEs have proven resilient to the crisis and are able to survive because, first, they have no foreign debt. Second, they have little debt to banks, as they are considered unbankable. Third, they use local inputs. Fourth, they are export-oriented. According to 2021 data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) of South Sulawesi Province, the contribution of MSMEs to gross

domestic product reached 54%-57%, their contribution to employment was around 66%, and 21% of MSMEs exported through third parties (exporters/intermediary traders). The data presented illustrates that micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are a driving force in development across all sectors, particularly those related to public welfare. However, the government, as a policymaker, needs to prioritize providing space for business development without creating regulations that could stifle business growth.

Economic development efforts in Makassar City are an integral part of national development efforts that must be implemented and harmonized in an integrated manner across sectors. To spur economic growth in Makassar City and achieve full employment, strategic steps are necessary. One way to do this is to encourage the growth of MSMEs, as this sector absorbs the largest workforce and encourages increased investment. To ensure these efforts are more effective, a study is needed on the development of the MSME sector in Makassar City. MSMEs operate in many business sectors, one of which is manufacturing. To see the growth in the number of MSMEs and their workforce absorption in Makassar City, see the following table:

Table 1: Development of MSMEs and Labor Absorption (2018-2022)

Year	Number of MSMEs	Number of Workers	Production Value (Rp)	Turnover Value (Rp)
2018	946 unit	1.204 person	11,38 M	14,79 M
2019	1054 unit	965 person	14.45 M	17,34 M
2020	1159 unit	861 person	13,14 M	14,45 M
2021	1273 unit	948 person	10,95 M	12,05 M
2022	1403 unit	758 person	13,69 M	14,38 M

Source: Makassar City Cooperatives and SMEs Office

Figure 1: Graph of development of MSME workforce absorption

In Makassar City, the manufacturing sector is the second-largest contributor to the city's GRDP after trade. The table above illustrates the number of workers, investment, and production value generated by small industries in Makassar City in 2021. In fact, with a relatively large number (1,490), or growth of approximately 17.83%, and an average annual increase in value added of 6.09% (2018-2022) (BPS South Sulawesi), MSMEs in the manufacturing sector have significant potential.

Analysis of the Impact of the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises in the Manufacturing Sector on Economic Growth in Makassar City. If developed, it is hoped that they will be able to absorb more labor and increase investment, thus increasing the scale of production of these MSMEs. Based on the phenomena described above, research on the Analysis of the Development of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in the Manufacturing Sector on Economic Growth in Makassar City is necessary.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1) Concept and Definition of MSMEs

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a crucial and strategic role in national economic development. In addition to contributing to economic growth and employment, MSMEs also play a role in distributing development outcomes. MSMEs have also proven resilient to crises. When the crisis struck in 1997-1998, only MSMEs were able to remain resilient.

Data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) shows that after the 1997-1998 economic crisis, the number of MSMEs did not decrease; in fact, it continued to increase, even absorbing 85 million to 107 million workers by 2012. In that year, the number of entrepreneurs in Indonesia reached 56,539,560. Of this number, 56,534,592, or 99.99%, were Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The remaining 0.01%, or 4,968 units, were large businesses. This data demonstrates that MSMEs represent a highly potential market for the financial services industry, particularly banks, for financing. Approximately 60-70% of MSMEs lack access to bank financing.

The government and legislature demonstrated their commitment to MSMEs by enacting Law No. 20 of 2021 concerning MSMEs. Classical issues, such as access to capital from financial institutions, are beginning to be addressed. This regulation stipulates the expansion of funding and facilitation by banks and non-bank financial services institutions. This regulation provides a larger portion for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. The government and legislature demonstrated their commitment to MSMEs by enacting Law No. 20 of 2018 concerning MSMEs. With this legal umbrella, MSMEs have become more flexible. Classical issues, such as access to capital from financial institutions, are beginning to be addressed. Banks are also becoming more aggressive in providing credit to MSMEs. MSMEs are no longer viewed as second-class businesses. Evidently, credit distribution to the MSME sector is gradually growing. In general, growth is higher than total bank credit. Figure 2. below, representing 2014 data, illustrates bank credit distribution. State-owned banks still hold the largest share, at 50%,

followed by national private banks at around 40%, regional development banks at 7%, and foreign banks and joint ventures at around 3%.

Figure 2: Graph of MSME Credit Distribution in 2021

Data from 2018 to 2021, as seen in Figure 3 below, clearly demonstrates a significant increase in bank lending to MSMEs. The average annual increase in MSME lending reached 13.63%. This is due to the active participation of banks in the development of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). The following illustrates general lending by commercial banks from 2011 to 2014, which serves as the initial basis for evaluating lending.

Figure 3: Graph of MSME Lending by Commercial Banks

2) Definition of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises

The definition of MSMEs is regulated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2008 concerning MSMEs. Chapter 1 (General Provisions), Article 1 of the Law, states that a micro enterprise is a productive business owned by an individual that meets the business criteria as stipulated in the Law. A small enterprise is an independent productive economic enterprise operated by an individual or business entity that is not a subsidiary or branch of a company owned, controlled, or part of, directly or indirectly, a Medium Enterprise (ME) or Large Enterprise (UB) that meets the criteria for a SME as defined in the Law.

Meanwhile, a SME is an independent productive economic enterprise operated by an individual or business entity that is not a subsidiary or branch of a company owned, controlled, or part of, directly or indirectly, a SME, UK, or UB that meets the criteria for a SME as defined in the Law. Based on the above criteria, a micro enterprise is a business unit with assets of up to IDR 50 million or annual sales of up to IDR 300 million. small businesses with assets worth more than 50 million up to a maximum of 500 million or have annual sales of more than IDR 300 million up to a maximum of IDR 2,500,000,000; and medium enterprises are companies with a net worth of more than Rp. 500 million to a maximum of Rp. 100 billion or have annual sales results of more than Rp. 2,500,000,000 to a maximum of Rp. 50 billion. are business units.

In the literature it is widely recognized that in developing countries, MSMEs are very important because of their main characteristics which are different from large businesses, namely: (1) The number of companies is very large (far exceeding the number of large businesses, especially from the category of micro and small businesses. In contrast to new businesses and medium businesses, micro and small businesses are spread throughout rural areas, including in relatively isolated areas. (2) Because they are very labor intensive, which means they have the potential for very large job growth opportunities, the growth of MSMEs can be included as an important element of national policy to increase job opportunities and create income, especially for the poor. (3) Not only are the majority of MSMEs, especially micro businesses, in developing countries, especially in rural areas. (4) MSMEs use technologies that are more appropriate to the proportion of production factors and conditions. Local resources in developing countries include abundant natural resources and a low-skilled workforce (although the numbers vary by country or region within a country), but limited capital and human resources, or highly educated workforce. (5) Many MSMEs are able to grow rapidly. In fact, many MSMEs survived the major Indonesian economic crisis of 1997/1998. (6) Although rural communities are generally poor, there is ample evidence that they can save and are willing to take risks by investing.

In this regard, MSMEs can be a starting point for mobilizing savings/investment in rural areas. (7) It has been proven that MSME entrepreneurs generally finance most of their business operations with personal savings, supplemented by assistance or loans from relatives or friends, informal lenders, traders or collectors, raw material suppliers, and advance payments from consumers. Therefore, these business groups can play another important role, namely as a means of channeling or allocating rural savings, which would otherwise be used for other purposes. unproductive. (8) Although many goods produced by MSMEs are also for the middle

and upper classes (albeit in small proportions), it is generally proven that the primary market for MSMEs is simple consumer goods at relatively low prices to meet the daily needs of the poor or low-income communities. However, many MSMEs also produce non-consumer goods such as production equipment, various simple machines, building materials, agriculture, construction, trade, tourism, and transportation. (9) As part of their dynamics, many MSMEs are also able to increase their productivity through investment and technological change.

According to Payne (in Rukminto, 2008: 77-78), empowerment is proposed as: "To help clients gain power of decision and action over their own lives by reducing the effect of social or personal blocks to exercising existing power, by increasing capacity and self-confidence to use power, and by transferring power from the environment to clients." Dimensions of Empowerment: To measure the extent of the influence of empowerment, Empowerment, there are several dimensions used to measure empowerment variables. According to Michael J. (2000), empowerment has five dimensions that can be used as measurement indicators, namely: Strength (Empowering), Protection (Protecting), Support (Supporting), Development (Fostering).

The Concept of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Small and medium enterprises are businesses that are independently owned and managed; these businesses do not always dominate the market. Small and medium enterprises are not part of or branches of other companies; they are run by the owners themselves, working freely according to their capabilities (Ebert and Griffin, 2005).

The Concept of Community Welfare Community welfare is a condition that reflects the state of a community's life, as seen from its standard of living. According to Todaro and Stephen C. Smith (2006), community welfare represents a measure of the results of community development in achieving a better life, which includes: first, increasing the ability and equitable distribution of basic needs such as food, housing, health, and protection; second, improved living standards, income levels, better education, and increased attention to culture and human values.

3) MSME Business Risk Management

Risk management is a logical and systematic method for identifying, analyzing, assessing, treating, monitoring, and communicating the risks inherent in every activity or function, or to minimize losses and maximize opportunities. Risk management is essentially carried out through the following processes: risk identification; risk evaluation and measurement; and risk management.

a. Risk Identification

Risk identification or risk identification is conducted to identify all risks faced by the company, such as identifying a fire in a workshop. Risk Evaluation and Measurement

The purpose of risk evaluation is to better understand the characteristics of risks, thus facilitating risk control. To measure risk, an approach can be used to estimate the likelihood (probability) of the risk and the level of risk consequence.

4) Understanding the People's Economy

The people's economy is the antithesis of the Taylorist mass-production-based conglomerate economic paradigm. Therefore, a network-based people's economy must adopt high technology as the factor providing the greatest added value to the economic process itself. The factors of scale and efficiency, which will form the basis of free competition, demand the involvement of people's economic networks, namely various centers of people's economic independence, large-scale people's economic independence, large-scale management patterns that adhere to the shortest cycle model in the form of what is often referred to as buyers.

Therefore, the people's economic system should not stop at the discourse level; several concrete agendas for the people's economy must be immediately brought to the surface. It is important to note that improving people's welfare in the context of the people's economy is not based on a locomotion paradigm, but rather on a foundational paradigm.

This means that welfare improvements no longer rely on the dominance of the central government, foreign capital, and conglomerate companies, but rather on the strength of local governments, fair competition, smallholder agricultural enterprises, and the role of genuine cooperatives, which are expected to serve as the foundation for strengthening the people's economy.

A development strategy that empowers the people's economy is a strategy for implementing economic democracy, where production is carried out by all, for all, and under the leadership and ownership of community members.

Brian Pratama (2015) is a leading figure in new institutional economics. Institutions are a pattern of relationships and structures between members of a community or organization that are mutually binding, facilitated by a business network. Brian's opinion, when linked to the existence of cooperative institutions, implies that there are binding rules or norms that must be

implemented in managing cooperatives. The Articles of Association (AD) and Bylaws (ART) serve as rules and guidelines for achieving goals. Similarly, Ronald H. Coase in 1991. The Nobel Prizes won by these two figures also fueled the development of new institutional economics in today's world. New institutional economic thinkers reject some of the assumptions of classical/neoclassical economics, deeming them unrealistic, such as zero transaction costs and instrumental rationality.

Charles B. Lowry and Paul J. Hanges (2018) argue that classical economics, which assumes all humans are rational and operate based on economic incentives, reveals that in practice, many social, economic, and political factors influence individuals in their economic decisions. Institutional economics explains that economic activity is strongly influenced by the layout of economic actors (political economy theory), the design of the rules of the game (transaction cost economic theory), the norms and beliefs of individuals/communities (social capital theory), incentives for collaboration (collective action theory), the model of agreements made (contract theory), the choice of ownership of physical and non-physical assets (property rights theory), and so on. In the current era of globalization, competition in the economic sector is increasingly fierce. Therefore, every change that occurs must be taken into account and anticipated.

5) The Concept of MSME Empowerment

According to Tri Winarni (2008), empowerment is: "To help clients gain power of decision and action over their own lives by reducing the effect of social or personal blocks to exercising existing power, by increasing capacity and self-confidence to use power, and by transferring power from the environment to clients."

Dimensions of Empowerment: To measure the extent of empowerment's influence, several dimensions are used to measure empowerment. According to Canet-Giner, Maria Teresa et al. (2010), MSME empowerment has five dimensions that can be used as measurement indicators: Empowering, Protecting, Supporting, and Fostering.

The Concept of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs): Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are businesses that are independently owned and managed; these businesses do not always dominate the market. Small and medium enterprises are not part of or branches of other companies; they are run by the owners themselves, working independently according to their abilities (Ebert and Griffin, 2005). The concept of community economic welfare is a condition that reflects the state of a community's life, as seen from its standard of living. According to Todaro and Stephen C. Smith (2006), community welfare represents a measure of the results of community development in achieving a better life, which includes: first, increasing capacity and equitable distribution of basic needs. such as food, housing, health and protection; second, an increase in the standard of living, income levels, better education, and increased attention to culture and human values.

The role of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Indonesian economy can be viewed from four aspects (Nurhajati, *New Paradigm for Developing Small and Medium Enterprises to Increase Economic Competitiveness*, (Malang: UNISMA), 2005, p. 2, namely: 1. Small and

Medium Enterprises (SMEs) constitute the largest part of all business units in Indonesia. 2. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a major role in absorbing labor. 3. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) make a significant contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The importance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) as stated above, directs the Government to undertake various efforts that simultaneously demonstrate a commitment to improving the performance and competitiveness of the Indonesian economy. This commitment is institutionally demonstrated through the establishment of a ministry that handles Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Nursalam, Empowerment of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): 2010, p. 4).

Legally, the Government's commitment is marked by the existence of Law Number: 9 of 1995 concerning Small Enterprises, which aims to Realizing the role of small businesses as the backbone and strengthening the national economic structure in facing global competition and fostering effective governance in the development of MSMEs.

This law was followed up by Government Regulation Number 44 of 1997 concerning Partnerships, as a way to create a business climate through collaboration between Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and Large Enterprises (Nursalam, 2010, pp. 5-6). Makassar City faces development challenges that include a growing population, limited land area, and the diversity of its community in terms of education, economics, and social aspects. One of the driving sectors of Makassar City's economy is the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1) Research Location

The research was conducted in Makassar City, South Sulawesi Province. This location was chosen because it is a trading center in Eastern Indonesia, with complex businesses and business actors from various regions, including business migrants from other countries (investors).

Another reason is that 87.17% of the real business sector in this area is comprised of MSMEs (source: Makassar City in 2017). Therefore, the majority of the population relies on this sector for their livelihood. It is hoped that the research results will serve as considerations for the local government in formulating short- and medium-term development plans that favor people-based economic development and the increased role of micro, small, and medium enterprises.

2) Data Types and Sources

The data obtained in this study include primary data sourced from empirical sources collected directly from the research location through direct observation, interviews, and questionnaire distribution. Secondary data is obtained through a literature review of books, journals, and other relevant documents. This type of research includes data obtained from relevant agencies (the Office of Cooperatives and SMEs, Investment and Trade, and the Makassar City Statistics

Office). Other data was obtained from micro-entrepreneurs in several business sectors, including culinary, fisheries, agriculture, and other home industries such as furniture and silver crafts.

3) Data Collection Techniques

The data collection techniques used were several methods, including interviews, questionnaire distribution, and literature review. The questionnaire distribution method was intended to determine and collect data on the number of sampled MSMEs and their workforce absorption, the business capital managed during the year, and the level of profit achieved. Data obtained through interviews included annual sales volume, business management costs, and the facilities and infrastructure supporting MSMEs in this area.

4) Data Analysis

Based on the data obtained from the research results, an analysis can be conducted to determine the level of community welfare and/or factors driving the growth of the people's economy in Makassar City, enabling MSMEs to support these development goals. This analysis hypothesizes that three variables influence community welfare and community economic development.

To determine the factors influencing community welfare and the role of MSMEs in Makassar City, a multiple regression analysis was conducted using the formula:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3 + \dots E_i$$

Where:

Y = Community Welfare

X1 = Labor Absorption

X2 = Marketing Profit

X3 = Operating Profit

b₀ = Estimated Parameter

This research method uses the approach used above to draw general conclusions from several observations of MSME variables in relation to community welfare and people's economic development. This study uses quantitative research, which seeks to determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables (X1, X2, and X3) on the level of community welfare (Y).

This analysis also outlines the most dominant variables influencing community welfare through the causal processes generated by the role of people's economic development at the macro level. To examine the results of the partial and simultaneous influence analysis, a multiple regression test using the formula above will yield calculated t-values and calculated F-values. If both the calculated t-value and the calculated F-value are greater than the t-value and F-value, H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Average Turnover of MSMEs in Makassar City

Based on the data in Table 1, MSMEs experienced growth over the five years 2014-2018. However, turnover declined by an average of 19.95% annually, followed by a 12.92% decline in average employment.

The sales turnover described is derived from Makassar City statistical data for 2018 and interviews with several micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) sampled in this study. Each year, 30% of the population was sampled using a questionnaire distributed through a collaborative team, including graduate management students as mentors. The following table shows the five-year turnover development.

Table 2: Production Value Development 2018-2022

Year	Production Value (Rp.)	(%)
2016	11,38 M	-
2017	14,45 M	+ 2,15 %
2018	13,14 M	-1,87 %
2019	10,95 M	-3,26 %
2020	13,69 M	+2,71 %

Source: Data after processing

Figure 5: Graph of business turnover development in MSMEs

2) Development of Investment and Capital for MSMEs

At the micro level, MSME businesses in Makassar City need to be developed because economic growth, both regionally and nationally, requires investment support. Given the limited investment and/or capital experienced by micro, small, and medium enterprises in

Makassar City, investment needs to be directed toward business sectors that rarely utilize imported raw materials. According to H. Rahman Bettada, a small business owner in the city, he stated that in the current economic conditions of the nation, especially in Makassar City, caution is needed when investing heavily in goods and services because consumer purchasing power is declining and business costs are increasing. The following describes the development of MSME investment in Makassar City over the past five years:

Table 3: Development of MSME Turnover in Makassar City

Year	Investment	(%)
2018	14,79 M	-
2019	17,34 M	+4,12 %
2020	14,45 M	-3,09 %
2021	12,05 M	-2,13 %
2022	14,38 M	-2,38 %

Source: Data after processing

Figure 6: Graph of MSME investment development

3) Development of MSME Labor Absorption

Some of the important roles of MSMEs in the growth of the people's economy in this region are their position as key players in economic activities across various sectors, namely: the largest provider of employment; a key player in the development of local economic activities and community empowerment; creators of new markets and sources of innovation; and their contribution to maintaining the balance of payments through export activities. Based on this description, the following is a depiction of MSME labor absorption over the past five years:

Table 4: Development of MSME Labor Absorption

Year	Labor Absorption	(%)
2018	1.204 orang	-
2019	965 orang	-19,85 %
2020	861 orang	-10,77 %
2021	948 orang	+10,11%
2022	758 orang	-20,04 %

Source: Data after processing

4) The Effect of Labor Absorption (X1), Business Capital (X2), and Profit (X3) on Community Welfare

Interpretation of the results of the following multiple data processing revealed the simultaneous influence of the three variables mentioned above as follows:

$$Y = 14.372 + 2.019 X1 + 2.546 X2 + 3.024 X3$$

The results of multiple regression analysis indicate that the empowerment of small and medium enterprises in Makassar City contributes 3.024 (X3) to economic development, followed by 2.546 (X2). This means that it has a significant impact on urban economic development in Makassar.

CONCLUSION

After conducting the research and discussion as presented in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- a) Through data analysis, the variable of labor absorption in MSMEs (X1) has a dominant influence on the level of community welfare in Makassar City.
- b) The variables of business capital and profit (X2 and X3) are next in importance in influencing the level of community welfare, with coefficient values of 2.546 and 3.024, respectively.
- c) The partial and simultaneous effects of all three variables are positive, with both the calculated t-test and calculated F-test being greater than the calculated t-test and F-test, respectively. In other words, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.
- d) The final conclusion is that the empowerment of micro, small, and medium enterprises is a key driver of regional economic growth and opens up employment opportunities, thereby reducing unemployment and improving community welfare.

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